

BIR O'LCHAMLI PANJARADA KOMPAKT QO'ZG'ALISHLI BILAPLASIANNING XOS QIYMATLARI ASIMPTOTIKASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda panjarada kompakt qo'zg'alishli diskret bilaplasianning muhim spektrdan tashqarida yagona xos qiymatga ega bo'lishi isbotlangan, hamda xos qiymat uchun yaqinlashuvchi asimptotik yoyilmalar olingan.

Kalit so'zlar. Diskret bilaplasian, xos qiymat, asimptotik yoyilma.

I. KIRISH

To'rtinchi tartibli elliptik operatorlar, xususan, bigarmonik operatorlar chiziqli elastiklik nazariyasi, mustahkamlik muammolari (masalan, osma ko'priklarni qurish) va Stoks oqimlarini tavsiflash kabi fizik modellarning keng sinfida muhim o'rin tutadi. Shu sababli qattiq jismlar fizikasi, kvant mexanikasi va elastiklik nazariyasida uchraydigan bigarmonik operatorlarning diskret va muhim spektriga oid tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirish muhim vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi. Panjaradagi bir zarrachali sistema gamiltonianlariga mos qo'zg'algan bigarmonik operatorlar oilalarining spektriga oid muammolarni hal etish matematik fizikada muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda [3], [4]. Bilaplasianlar chiziqli elastiklik nazariyasi, mustahkamlik muammolari, optimallashtirilgan va yetarlicha siyrak saqlangan ma'lumotli tasvirlarni siqishda yuqori potentsialga ega bo'ladi.

II. MUAMMONING BAYONI VA ASOSIY NATIJALARI

Faraz qilaylik, \mathbb{Z} - bir o'lchamli panjara, $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$ - orqali \mathbb{Z} da aniqlangan kvadrati bilan jamlanuvchi funksiyalarning Hilbert fazosini belgilaymiz. $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z})$ Hilbert fazosida

$$\hat{h}_\mu = \hat{h}_0 - \mu \hat{v}, \quad \mu > 0,$$

formula yordamida aniqlangan o'z-o'ziga qo'shma chegaralangan operatorlar oilasini qaraymiz. Bu yerda \hat{h}_0 - diskret bilaplacian, ya'ni

$$\hat{h}_0 = \hat{\Delta} \hat{\Delta}$$

bunda

$$(\hat{\Delta} \hat{f})(x) = \hat{f}(x) - \frac{\hat{f}(x+1) + \hat{f}(x-1)}{2}, \quad \hat{f} \in \ell^2(\mathbb{Z}),$$

diskret laplacian va \hat{v} esa rangi birga teng bo'lgan operator

$$(\hat{v} \hat{f})(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{4} (\hat{f}(1) - \hat{f}(-1)), & x = 1 \\ \frac{1}{4} (\hat{f}(1) - \hat{f}(-1)), & x = -1 \\ 0, & x \neq \pm 1 \end{cases}$$

Faraz qilaylik, $\mathbb{T} = (-\pi, \pi]$ bir o'lchamli tor, $L^2(\mathbb{T})$ - \mathbb{T} da kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi funksiyalarning Hilbert fazosi bo'lsin. \hat{h}_μ operator impuls ko'rinish quyidagi

$$h_\mu = h_0 - \mu \mathbf{v}, \quad \mu > 0,$$

formula yordamida aniqlanadi, bunda h_0

$$\varepsilon(p) := (1 - \cos p)^2$$

funksiyaga ko'paytirish operatori va \mathbf{v} rangi birga teng bo'lgan operator

$$(\mathbf{v}f)(p) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} \sin p \sin q f(q) dq.$$

Tushunarliki,

$$\sigma(h_0) = \sigma_{\text{ess}}(h_0) = [0, 4],$$

\mathbf{v} ning kompakt operator ekanligidan klassik Weyl teoremasiga asosan barcha $\mu > 0$

$$\sigma_{\text{ess}}(h_\mu) = \sigma_{\text{ess}}(h_0) = [0, 4]$$

tenglik bajariladi.

Teorema. *Ixtiyoriy $\mu > 0$ uchun h_μ operator muhim spektrdan tashqarida yotadigan yagona $e(\mu) < 0$ xos qiymatga ega va unga mos xos funksiya quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi*

$$f_\mu(p) := \frac{\sin p}{\varepsilon(p) - e(\mu)}$$

Shuningdek:

- $\mu \in (0, +\infty) \mapsto e(\mu)$ funksiya haqiqiy analitik, qat'iy kamayuvchi, $(0, +\infty)$ da qat'iy botiq

va

$$\lim_{\mu \rightarrow 0} e(\mu) = 0 \quad \text{va} \quad \lim_{\mu \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{e(\mu)}{\mu} = -\frac{1}{2},$$

- yetarlicha kichik va musbat μ lar uchun

$$(-e(\mu))^{\frac{1}{4}} = 2^{-3}\mu - 2^{-11}(2^8 + 1)\mu^2 - 2^{-11}(2^8 - 1)\mu^3 + \sum_{n \geq 3} D_n \mu^{n+1}$$

tenglik o'rinli, bu yerda $D_n, n = 1, 2, \dots$, haqiqiy koeffitsentlar.

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